

Table SM2. Mean and SE values for density (ind.m⁻²) and biomass (g wet weight m⁻²) of the benthic macrofauna of the continental slope and São Paulo plateau according to transects (A-H) in Santos Basin, SW Atlantic.

Transect	A		B		C		D		E		F		G		H	
	mean	SE														
Density (ind.m ⁻²)																
Annelida	1601	604	1250	345	1874	488	1672	516	1275	446	1307	423	1939	730	2832	1161
Crustacea	396	101	330	74	490	99	379	103	303	70	394	143	353	94	772	220
Mollusca	85	17	143	40	147	43	214	83	141	45	432	346	97	29	186	88
Other	140	35	144	46	179	44	129	37	115	34	126	40	129	43	219	54
Biomass (g WW m ⁻²)																
Annelida	0.703	0.256	0.457	0.123	0.747	0.283	0.560	0.173	0.357	0.099	0.445	0.151	0.623	0.177	1.403	0.584
Crustacea	0.074	0.026	0.049	0.012	0.093	0.026	0.087	0.046	0.102	0.055	0.095	0.042	0.088	0.042	0.162	0.055
Mollusca	0.060	0.018	0.112	0.035	0.073	0.017	0.125	0.067	0.100	0.042	0.248	0.179	0.136	0.049	0.185	0.116
Other	0.010	0.003	0.008	0.003	0.013	0.003	0.010	0.003	0.006	0.002	0.011	0.004	0.010	0.005	0.019	0.005